

SIMULATION AND TOMOGRAPHY ANALYSES OF TEXTILE COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

A simulation method for woven composite fabric deformation at mesoscopic scale is presented together with a specific continuum hypo-elastic constitutive model. X-ray tomography is used to obtain undeformed and deformed 3D geometries of the reinforcement. Comparisons between numerical and experimental 3D deformed geometries are shown.

Keywords: Composite Forming; Finite Element Analysis; X-Ray tomography; meso-scale; Mechanical Properties

INTRODUCTION

The Liquid Composite Moulding processes for composite consist in three stages. A dry textile reinforcement is formed (pre-forming stage), then the resin is injected within this preform and finally, cured to obtain the final composite part. During the first stage, the reinforcement can undergo large deformations, especially when it is doubly curved shaped. In such a case, the reinforcement can be subjected to large in-plane distortions which can reach values up to 40°. These deformations modify the mechanical properties but also the permeability of the reinforcement.

The present contribution presents a method for the simulation of the deformation of a woven composite reinforcement representative unit cell (i.e. at the mesoscopic scale). These simulations enable to determine the macroscopic scale mechanical behaviour of dry composite reinforcements (without resin) at finite strain. This information is required in finite element simulations of the pre-forming stage. Besides, knowing the deformed geometry of the woven cell enables to determine the permeability of the fibrous reinforcement via Stokes (or Stokes-Brinkman) flow simulations within this deformed cell. Finally, the geometry of the deformed reinforcement heavily influences the mechanical behaviour of the final composite part.

The local geometry of the woven reinforcement can be determined experimentally using X-ray tomography. The advantage of tomography is to give access to local 3D observations inside the sample which is not possible with standard microscopy techniques restrained to surface observations. X-ray tomography is used in the present contribution at mesoscopic scale (the scale of the yarns) to determine the initial and deformed geometry of fibrous composite reinforcements and at microscopic scale (the scale of the fibres) to determine the density and distribution of fibres within the yarn.

The information gathered from these experiments is used to improve and justify the assumptions made during the development of the mechanical constitutive model and above all to validate the results obtained from simulations.

Here, the yarn is assumed to be a continuum. The mechanical behaviour of this continuum is very specific since the yarn is made up of thousands of fibres which can move with respect to each other. The suggested constitutive model is a hypo-elastic one. The objective derivative of this model is defined from the local fibre rotation so that it accurately tracks the fibre direction. The transverse behaviour of the yarns is of a great importance because local crushing has a significant impact during the deformation.

X-RAY TOMOGRAPHY

The local geometry of the woven reinforcement can be determined experimentally using X-ray tomography. As previously mentioned, the advantage of tomography is to give access to local 3D observations inside the sample.

Brief material description

The principle is analogous to the medical scanner and allows from X-ray radiography to reconstruct non destructively the internal structure of an opaque material [1]. The reconstruction involves a computed step and the final image is a 3D map of the local X-ray attenuation coefficient. The fibres absorbing much more the X-rays than the air, the attenuation contrast allows a straightforward subsequent thresholding of the images.

The laboratory tomograph used in the present study is a commercial model [2] which includes a nanofocus transmission X-ray tube (W target). The size of the focus (and thus the resolution) is tunable from 1 to 5 microns. The detector used is a 1500x1900 array of amorphous silicon sensible elements each of a lateral size of 127x127 microns. The beam has been operated at 90 keV and 170 μ A with no filtering for the observations made in this study. The setup used exhibiting a cone beam geometry, it is easy to obtain images at different values of the magnification. For this purpose, the sample is simply placed at different distances from the source leading to a possible voxel size of 1.5 to 80 microns in the resulting reconstruction.

High resolution observations

Images at high resolution provide information about the location of fibres: their relative position or the spatial distribution of their local density. From the comparison of figures 1a, 1b and 1c it can be noticed that the fibre bundle tends to be denser in the deformed state for both biaxial tension and shear. The fibre distribution appears to be at random in each of the three cases. A quantitative analysis of the morphology of these images has been performed with the same procedure as in [3]. For that, the covariance $C(x)$, that is to say, the probability for two points, separated by the distance x , to belong to the same phase, namely the phase of the fibres, has been evaluated. When calculated in two perpendicular directions (namely along the width and along the thickness of each yarn), the covariograms provide information about the spatial distribution of fibres within the yarn.

Figure 1. Glass plain weave (a) unloaded (3 μm resolution, rescaled) (b) biaxial tension (5 μm resolution) and (c) 46° pure shear (2.85 μm resolution rescaled)

If the covariograms look similar in both directions, the sample can be assumed to be isotropic. Fig. 2 presents the curves of the covariance in directions 2 and 3 averaged over several measurements, each performed on four different yarn cross sections and at twenty-two different locations containing about 70 fibres in each case.

Figure 2. Average covariance in direction 2 and 3 computed from 20 observation zones (black squares on this slice) on four slices of deformed yarns.

These curves show that the first minimum (corresponding to the average position of the air gap between two fibres) and the first maximum (a measure of the average position of the first neighbouring fibre) of the curves are located at similar distances in both directions indicating an isotropic spacing of the fibres. Such observation is a strong

support to validate the assumption of a quasi-isotropic distribution of the fibres in the transverse plane during the deformation of a bundle.

Undeformed and deformed geometries

Undeformed geometries but also deformed geometries can be analyzed. Three types of woven reinforcements are shown. The first one is a thin interlock reinforcement hereafter referred to as G1151[®]. Its large unit cell is reconstructed with a resolution of 20 microns (see Fig. 3a). The reconstruction of an undeformed 2x2 carbon twill (10 μ m resolution) is also shown in figure 3b.

Figure 3. G1151[®] (a) and 2x2 carbon twill (b) 3D reconstruction and various cutting planes in the warp and weft direction

Images of the undeformed interlock reinforcement underline the complexity of the woven structure characterized by non trivial initial geometries. One can for instance observe that even in the undeformed case, superimposed weft yarns generally do not lie in the same plane. Moreover, a wide variety of cross section shapes can be observed on a single yarn depending on the location inside the fabric. These cross sections can be elliptic, almost flat, or quasi rectangular in some cases.

MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

Constitutive model

The constitutive model is written within the framework of a rate constitutive equation (or hypo-elasticity) [4]. Based on the high resolution observations mentioned above, the mechanical behaviour of the yarn is assumed to be transversely.

The two main aspects of the constitutive model are: the longitudinal and transverse behaviours and the choice of the working frame.

The mechanical behaviour of the yarn is assumed to be transversely isotropic in the direction perpendicular to that of the fibres, hereafter denoted as $\underline{\mathbf{f}}_1$. It can be noted that some work on rather different systems i.e. particular reinforced composites had already shown that if the spatial distribution of the reinforcement of a composite is at random and thus isotropic, the isotropy tends to be preserved after deformation.

A hypo-elastic constitutive equation (or rate constitutive equation) has the following form:

$$\underline{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}}^{\nabla} = \underline{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}} : \underline{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}} \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}}^{\nabla}$, $\underline{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}}$ are respectively the Cauchy stress objective rate tensor, the strain rate tensor and the constitutive tensor. This equation is integrated over a time increment $\Delta t = t^{n+1} - t^n$ using the formula of Hughes and Winget [5] widely used in finite element codes at finite strains:

$$\left[\underline{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}}^{n+1} \right]_{\mathbf{e}_i^{n+1}} = \left[\underline{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}}^n \right]_{\mathbf{e}_i^n} + \left[\underline{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}}^{n+1/2} \right]_{\mathbf{e}_i^{n+1/2}} \left[\underline{\underline{\underline{\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}}} \right]_{\mathbf{e}_i^{n+1/2}} \quad (2)$$

where $\left[\underline{\underline{\underline{\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}}} \right]_{\mathbf{e}_i^{n+1/2}} = \left[\underline{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}} \right]_{\mathbf{e}_i^{n+1/2}} \Delta t$ and $\left[\underline{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}} \right]_{\mathbf{e}_i^n}$ stands for the matrix of the components of any tensor $\underline{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}}$ expressed in the basis $\mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_j \otimes \dots \otimes \mathbf{e}_m$ at time t^n . $\{\underline{\mathbf{e}}_i\} = \{\underline{\mathbf{e}}_1, \underline{\mathbf{e}}_2, \underline{\mathbf{e}}_3\}$ is the orthonormal rotating basis, the rotation of which is used to compute the objective derivatives.

Objective derivative

The very large longitudinal stiffness of the fibres requires to strictly monitoring their direction under the risk of cumulating significant spurious stresses at each time step. Therefore the rotating basis, denoted as $\{\underline{\mathbf{f}}_i\}$ in the present case of fibrous material, must be attached to $\underline{\mathbf{f}}_1$ the fibre direction, which means using a rotational objective derivative based on the fibre rotation [6]. An interesting consequence is that the constitutive matrix of eq. 2 is then expressed in the basis oriented by the fibre direction at current time. This is a major advantage because its shape and its components are known or can be determined in this basis where longitudinal and transverse behaviours are distinguished. The first one is defined by the stiffness of the fibres in direction $\underline{\mathbf{f}}_1$ whereas the second one characterizes the behaviour of the fibre bundle in plane $(\underline{\mathbf{f}}_2, \underline{\mathbf{f}}_3)$.

Transverse behaviour

An important issue for mesoscopic analyzes accounts for shape changes of the yarn cross section. As seen in the X-ray imaging, the yarns tend to be transversely crushed in any type of loading. These local effects play a major role for the macroscopic mechanical behaviour of the reinforcement. It is suggested in the present approach to uncouple ‘‘spherical’’ and deviatoric phenomena within the transverse plane. In two dimensions, the term ‘‘spherical’’ is a misuse of language, but we use it for convenience in the following. This separation is supported by tomography scans where two modes of

deformation of the cross section are clearly distinguished: compaction of the network of fibres (for instance in biaxial tension, Fig 1b) and rearrangement or change of shape of the fibre bundle (noticeable in pure shear, Fig 1c). These two modes correspond to spherical and deviatoric transformations of the cross section: the spherical part of the deformation is related to the fibre density changes and the deviatoric part to the shape changes. In the following, it is considered that these two modes are uncoupled.

Let us separate longitudinal and transverse deformations within the strain tensor:

$$[\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}]_{f_i} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} & \varepsilon_{12} & \varepsilon_{13} \\ & 0 & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & \varepsilon_{22} & \varepsilon_{23} \\ \text{sym.} & & \varepsilon_{33} \end{bmatrix} = [\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_L]_{f_i} + [\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_T]_{f_i} \quad (3)$$

where $\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$, here, stands for the tensorial cumulation of $\underline{\mathbf{D}}\Delta t$ in the rotating frame. The following developments only concern the plane $(\underline{\mathbf{f}}_2, \underline{\mathbf{f}}_3)$ and the restriction of $[\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_T]_{f_i}$ to $(\underline{\mathbf{f}}_2, \underline{\mathbf{f}}_3)$ is considered:

$$[\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_T]_{f_i} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{22} & \varepsilon_{23} \\ \text{sym.} & \varepsilon_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_T]_{f_i} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{22} & \varepsilon_{23} \\ \text{sym.} & \varepsilon_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_s & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_s \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_d & \varepsilon_{23} \\ \varepsilon_{23} & \varepsilon_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $\varepsilon_s = \frac{\varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33}}{2}$ is the spherical strain component and $\varepsilon_d = \frac{\varepsilon_{22} - \varepsilon_{33}}{2}$, ε_{23} are the deviatoric ones. This formalism where spherical and deviatoric parts are uncoupled is very often used in plasticity models. It has also been used in fibre bundle micromechanics [7].

The model is considered as (non linear) elastic then the same separation is valid for stresses. Moreover, since integration is a linear operation, this separation also holds for strain and stress increments $[\Delta \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_T]_{f_i}$ and $[\Delta \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_T]_{f_i}$. Thus the suggested uncoupling leads to the following relations:

$$\Delta \sigma_s = A \Delta \varepsilon_s \quad \Delta \sigma_d = B \Delta \varepsilon_d \quad \Delta \sigma_{23} = B \Delta \varepsilon_{23} \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta \sigma_s$, $\Delta \sigma_d$, $\Delta \varepsilon_s$ and $\Delta \varepsilon_d$ are respectively spherical and deviatoric stress and strain increments (stress components being defined in the same way as strain components by eq. (4)), and A, B are the elastic coefficients. Eventually the transverse constitutive tensor contains two independent elastic coefficients, which corresponds to an isotropic two dimensional medium: (using Voigt notation):

$$[\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_T]_{f_i} = \begin{bmatrix} (A+B)/2 & (A-B)/2 & 0 \\ (A-B)/2 & (A+B)/2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

To complete the description of this model, the form of the coefficients A and B must be specified. To this aim, we use basic physical assumptions. Under compaction the material becomes stiffer in both spherical and deviatoric behaviours due to a densification of the fibre network (up to the maximum achievable density). Note also that under longitudinal tension, the spherical behaviour should be stiffer. For the sake of

simplicity, it is considered in the present model that tension has no influence on the deviatoric behaviour. From these assumptions, it is suggested to give the following form to coefficients A and B:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= A_0 e^{-p\varepsilon_s} e^{n\varepsilon_{11}} \\ B &= B_0 e^{-p\varepsilon_s} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Finally, the transverse constitutive model requires four parameters.

Mesoscopic simulations of reinforcement deformation

In order to perform mesoscopic scale simulations of the mechanical behaviour of composite reinforcements, the geometry of the model has to be defined. It must insure that there are neither unexpected penetrations nor spurious voids between the yarns. The results of Hivet [8] provide a convenient and ready-to-use way to deal with this issue. Moreover, the periodicity of the reinforcement is used to set the size of the geometric model. The smallest geometry to be modelled is that of a representative unit cell of the reinforcement, i.e. the smallest pattern permitting reconstructing the whole fabric by translations only. Its choice is not unique. Nevertheless considering the application of boundary conditions, the choice of a unit cell with material boundaries is preferred (see figure 4).

Figure 4. Representative Unit Cell for a plain weave for pure shear loading

The periodicity of the reinforcement must be guaranteed during the test, which is achieved through appropriate boundary conditions. It has been extensively explained in [9]. In some particular cases like biaxial tension tests, the symmetry properties of the reinforcement and the test kinematics allow reducing the size of the model. This is not the case for pure shear because the symmetries of the geometry vanish due to the kinematics of shear.

COMPARISONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The material constitutive model introduced in the previous section is implemented in a user subroutine VUMAT of Abaqus/Explicit. The material coefficients are determined

from different experimental tests. The longitudinal Young modulus E_1 is known from a tension test on a single yarn. The determination of the transverse behaviour four parameters A_0 , B_0 , n , p is performed through an inverse method [10] based on a test that leads to significantly crushing the yarns. To keep the yarn bending stiffness low, the longitudinal shear moduli G_{12} and G_{13} are significantly lower than the longitudinal Young's modulus and assumed to have equal values: $G_{12} = G_{13} = G_1$. Longitudinal Poisson ratios are assumed to be null. The values used for the simulations are mentioned in table 1.

Table 1. Material parameters used for glass plain weave simulations.

Longitudinal Young modulus E_1 (MPa)	52500
Transverse parameter A_0 (MPa)	1.86 E-3
Transverse parameter B_0 (MPa)	6.25 E-3
Transverse parameter n	4060
Transverse parameter p	39.9
Longitudinal shear modulus G_1 (MPa)	20

Comparisons between numerical and experimental cross sections

Due to a slight variability of cross section shapes observed either in undeformed or biaxial tensioned states, it is necessary to compute average cross section shapes. Based on 30 different cross sections extracted from the sample comparisons have been made between numerical and experimental crushing ratios but also global final shapes for the three cited types of woven textiles.

Fig. 5 shows the averaged cross sections in the initial state and after an equi-biaxial tension with a load of 11 N applied to each yarn. These cross sections are compared to those obtained from simulation. Though the initial geometry is slightly different at the tips due to the use of brick elements, the agreement is satisfying. The crushing ratios of the yarn cross section are very close: 12.5% for the simulation versus 13.3% measured by tomography.

Figure 5. Comparison between experimental and numerical yarn cross sections for 11N equi-biaxial tension.

The scans of the sheared reinforcement are performed at a scale of 2.85 microns and under a shear angle of 46° . Fig. 6 shows the comparison between scans and simulation at the same shear angle for a sequence of transverse cross sections of the yarn. Several interesting trends are to be noticed. The computed cross section is significantly compacted along the width of the yarns as is the actual one. In addition, the model captures well the distortions and dissymmetries of the section occurring due to shear of the reinforcement.

Figure 6. Comparison of simulation with X-ray scans for a set of yarn cross sections along $\frac{1}{2}$ period of the yarn for 46° shear angle.

The macroscopic behaviour of the reinforcement, namely the shear behaviour and biaxial tension behaviour can also be obtained from these analyzes. All of these results extracted from simulations are necessary in many applications like flow simulation within deformed reinforcements, finite element pre-forming simulation. The mesoscopic shape of the fibrous reinforcement is also very important in critical areas of the final composite.

Conclusion and future works

An approach is proposed for the simulation of woven composite fabric deformation at mesoscopic scale. A rate constitutive model based on the objective derivative defined by the rotation of the fibres is used. Simulations woven unit cell deformations in biaxial tension and in-plane shear have been compared with tomography analyzes. The results are in good agreement. Another on going aspect of this work is about coupling with resin flow simulation tools. The geometry of the deformed cell allows obtaining permeability values taking into account the deformation due to performing.

Simulations of a plain weave unit cell deformation in biaxial tension and in-plane shear have been compared with tomography analyzes. The results are in good agreement.

Further analyzes are currently performed to compare the simulations for more complex reinforcements like the interlock G1151 or 2x2 carbon twill.

Another on going aspect of this work is about coupling with resin flow simulation tools. The geometry of the deformed cell allows obtaining permeability values taking into account the deformation due to performing. This deformation significantly influences these values.

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